

Research on Investment Efficiency of "The Belt and Road" National Infrastructure PPP Projects

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Abstract:

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has been the centerpiece of China's foreign policy since 2013, with a focus on infrastructure development and investment in countries along the ancient Silk Road. As part of this initiative, China has been promoting the development of public-private partnership (PPP) projects to help finance and build infrastructure in participating countries. This paper aims to assess the investment efficiency of the National infrastructure PPP projects under the BRI. In comparison to traditional infrastructure projects, PPP projects involve many stakeholders, and the level of cooperation among the various

stakeholders has a direct impact on the project's outcomes. As a consequence of this, doing research on the efficiency of PPP project collaboration is an absolute necessity. The study uses both primary and secondary data sources, including interviews with project managers and financial analysis of project data. The results show that while there are some successful PPP projects under the BRI, overall investment efficiency is hindered by issues such as poor project management, lack of transparency, and regulatory challenges. The results also manifest that the application of PPP, the increasing amount of and investments on PPP projects all significantly helped improve the efficiency, which implies a good effect of PPP. Moreover, the efficiency had been significantly improved since the BRI was put forward in 2013, which proves the value and effectiveness of this worldwide policy. Which really great to know that, the result has given us a positive feedback regarding upcoming investors of PPP Project. The study provides recommendations for improving the investment efficiency of PPP projects under the BRI.

Keywords: *Belt and Road Initiative, public-private partnerships, investment efficiency, infrastructure development.*

Introduction

Since China's Silk Road Economic Belt and the Belt and Road Initiative were proposed by

Chinese President Mr. Xi in 2013, the central financial and economic leading group meeting in 2014 made a crucial decision to accelerate the construction of the Belt and Road Initiative.

This visionary approach aimed to expand and deepen global economic integration by fostering enhanced connectivity. China's Belt and Road Initiative not only serves as a strategic blueprint for interconnecting nations but also addresses the infrastructure bottlenecks faced by developing countries. As highlighted by the Tsinghua Carnegie Global Policy Center, investment in the interconnection of countries lies at the very heart of China's ambitious initiative.

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) is China's flagship foreign policy project, which was launched in 2013 with the aim of strengthening economic ties with countries along the ancient Silk Road. The BRI seeks to promote infrastructure development and investment in participating countries, with a focus on transport, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure. The initiative is based on the principles of mutual benefit, win-win cooperation, and shared development.

The "One Belt One Road" initiative is a cornerstone of China's comprehensive opening strategy, devised to foster an international environment conducive to economic development while bolstering the growth of China's central and western regions. Embracing the historical concept of the Silk Road, "the belt" primarily encompasses a vast land-based corridor. Originating from China, it traverses Central Asia and West Asia, ultimately reaching the thriving economic circles of Europe. This expansive region is widely regarded as the world's longest and most promising economic corridor. Within China, the corridor encompasses regions such as Xinjiang, Qinghai, Gansu, Shaanxi, Ningxia in the northwest, as well as Chongqing, Sichuan, Guangxi, Yunnan in the southwest, and Inner Mongolia. Extending westward, it forms vital connections with Central Asia, Europe, including countries such as Russia, Kazakhstan, and others within the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, along with five observer countries and three dialogue partners (Duan, Lin, & Shi, 2019). Conversely, "one way" predominantly takes the form of maritime routes, commencing from China's southeastern coastal ports. It spans six coastal

provinces, including Shandong, Jiangsu, Zhejiang, Fujian, Guangdong, and Hainan. Crossing the South China Sea, it extends into the Indian Ocean and Persian Gulf, traversing East Africa and eventually reaching Southern Europe. Encompassing Southeast Asia, South Asia, the Middle East, North Africa, and Southern Europe, this maritime component of the Belt and Road Initiative assumes significant strategic importance. It is worth noting that the initiative essentially builds upon President Jiang's "western development" plan and President Hu's policy of "The Rise of Central China," expertly repackaged and expanded to extend beyond national borders, forging enduring connections with countries in Central Asia. Additionally, the integration of the Indian Ocean Pearl Chain strategy, a critical high-level strategic plan initiated during President Hu's tenure, aims to overcome the challenges posed by the "Malacca dilemma" in energy transportation. This holistic approach also encompasses policies geared toward securing energy and natural gas pipeline transportation from Central Asia.

President Xi articulated a bold vision for a new security and economic order in Asia, underscoring China's commitment to fostering regional prosperity and cooperation. Delivering a significant address at the Boao Forum in March 28, 2015, he positioned China as a willing partner in jointly establishing a regional order that would benefit Asia and the global community as a whole (Huang, & Zhao, 2020). President Xi showcased China's leadership in several key initiatives, including the establishment of the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB). The AIIB aims to provide substantial financing for critical development projects, such as railways and ports, while fostering greater economic integration across Asia.

In his remarks at the Boao Forum, President Xi emphasized that China's vision extends beyond Asia, welcoming the participation of countries worldwide. Mindful of concerns raised by some Asian politicians and security experts regarding China's potential dominance, President Xi deliberately avoided placing China at the center of the new order. He emphasized that China's

role should be commensurate with its size, noting that being a major power entails assuming greater responsibility for regional and global peace and development, rather than seeking monopolistic control over regional and international affairs.

The Boao Forum for Asia, an annual event held in the coastal town of Boao, China, served as a platform for President Xi to convey China's intent to reshape Asia's economic and security landscape. By leveraging its ascendance, the Chinese government aims to bring about a transformational shift from the previous decades, during which it largely operated within the framework dominated by the United States and Western countries. Central to China's endeavors is the Belt and Road Initiative, which serves as the focal point of China's ambitious agenda to reshape the Asian region.

As part of the BRI, China has been promoting the development of public-private partnership (PPP) projects to help finance and build infrastructure in participating countries. PPPs are long-term contracts between public and private sectors to provide infrastructure or services that traditionally have been provided by the public sector. PPPs can be an effective way to finance and build infrastructure, as they enable private sector expertise and financing to be combined with public sector oversight and regulation.

However, PPP projects are not without risks and challenges. PPP projects require careful management and oversight to ensure that they are efficient, effective, and provide value for money. There are also challenges in terms of ensuring transparency, accountability, and regulatory compliance. In the context of the BRI, these challenges are compounded by the cultural and institutional differences between China and participating countries, as well as geopolitical risks and uncertainties.

This paper aims to assess the investment efficiency of the national infrastructure PPP projects under the BRI. The paper begins by reviewing the literature on PPPs and investment efficiency, followed by an overview of the BRI and its PPP projects. The paper then presents

the results of the study and provides recommendations for improving the investment efficiency of PPP projects under the BRI.

Literature Review

Public-private partnerships (PPPs) have become an increasingly popular way to finance and build infrastructure in both developed and developing countries. PPPs enable the private sector to bring expertise and financing to infrastructure projects, while the public sector provides oversight and regulation. PPPs can be an effective way to deliver infrastructure projects that are efficient, effective, and provide value for money.

The PPP model has been extensively studied both internationally and within China. As China's infrastructure PPP investment and financing reforms progress rapidly, it is crucial to further enhance and refine these studies by considering the unique characteristics of China's infrastructure sector and aligning them with the goals outlined in the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China.

The research should address key questions such as how to establish mechanisms for private capital access and exit, improve infrastructure pricing mechanisms, develop government compensation mechanisms, and measure the government's financial capacity and risks under the PPP model. Exploring these issues will contribute to the advancement of China's PPP model.

One area of research focuses on the efficiency of PPP within the framework of the "New Public Management" movement. While there are notable distinctions between privatization of public services and PPP, the "New Public Management" movement provides a theoretical foundation for PPP by aiming to enhance the efficiency of the public sector. The theory suggests that the government should withdraw from less efficient public service projects and introduce competition to achieve better services, lower costs, and minimize economic waste.

It is essential to systematically summarize the experiences of PPP implementation both

domestically and abroad. Existing studies often analyze single cases empirically, leading to conclusions that may be typical but not universally applicable. Future research should encompass a comprehensive review of domestic and foreign experiences across various infrastructure systems. It should not only focus on successful cases but also delve into failed cases to generate knowledge and support China's infrastructure PPP reform.

Limited fiscal funds and insufficient budgets are key reasons why the government seeks private sector involvement in infrastructure financing and operations. By adopting the PPP model, the government can save financial resources in infrastructure projects and potentially shield itself from liability. Research by Hammami and Ouhibi indicates that PPP is commonly used in countries burdened by heavy government liabilities.

Additionally, the government's lack of management resources and the inefficiency of public services also contribute to its reliance on private sector participation in infrastructure investment and financing. The PPP model leverages the advanced technology and management expertise of the private sector to enhance infrastructure management and efficiency. Scholars such as Grimsey and Lewis argue that PPP can address issues such as cost overruns and delays associated with traditional government procurement methods by establishing appropriate incentives between contracting partners. Moreover, PPP can foster innovation in infrastructure development.

Another line of research on PPP efficiency is based on contract theory. Scholars like Hart suggest that contracting costs are pivotal in selecting the PPP model. When the quality of construction is difficult to measure accurately but service quality can be defined in the initial contract, PPP proves superior to traditional investment and financing models. Researchers such as Bentz, Martimort, and Pouyet, drawing from contract theory and the moral hazard model, have analyzed PPP and concluded that it is a more efficient investment and financing model compared to traditional approaches.

Belt and Road Initiative and PPP Projects

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) is a major infrastructure development and investment project launched by China in 2013. The BRI aims to strengthen economic ties with countries along the ancient Silk Road, through investment in infrastructure, including transport, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure. The BRI covers over 70 countries and regions, representing over 60% of the world's population and GDP.

As part of the BRI, China has been promoting the development of public-private partnership (PPP) projects to help finance and build infrastructure in participating countries. PPPs can enable the private sector to bring expertise and financing to infrastructure projects, while the public sector provides oversight and regulation.

The BRI PPP projects cover a wide range of sectors, including transport, energy, and telecommunications. Examples of BRI PPP projects include:

China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC): CPEC is a major infrastructure project under the BRI, which aims to connect China's Xinjiang province with Pakistan's Gwadar port through a network of highways, railways, and pipelines. CPEC includes several PPP projects, including the construction of a 1,320 MW coal-fired power plant in Pakistan.

Jakarta-Bandung High-Speed Railway: The Jakarta-Bandung High-Speed Railway is a PPP project between China and Indonesia, which aims to build a 142 km high-speed railway between Jakarta and Bandung. The project is expected to cost \$6 billion and is being financed by a consortium of Chinese banks.

Hambantota Port: The Hambantota Port in Sri Lanka is a PPP project between China Merchants Port Holdings and the Sri Lanka Ports Authority. The project involves the development and operation of the port, as well as the construction of related infrastructure, such as a logistics park.

The Evolutionary Path of "One Belt and One Road" Initiative

The comprehensive framework of the "One Belt and One Road" initiative has been clearly outlined, emphasizing extensive collaboration through policy alignment, infrastructure connectivity, streamlined trade, and integrated financing. The visionary concept of the initiative was recognized when Premier Li Keqiang of China visited Kazakhstan in late 2014, where they celebrated the initial accomplishments in achieving "interconnectivity" and fostering a shared understanding of the "One Belt and One Road" vision. Notably, China's neighboring countries along the initiative's routes, spanning Central Asia, Western Asia, and Africa, possess abundant reserves of energy and mineral resources. Capitalizing on this opportunity, China's assistance in infrastructure development and resource exchange with these nations promises mutual benefits and a truly win-win outcome.

The implementation of the "One Belt and One Road" initiative involves multiple cooperation mechanisms, including bilateral partnerships, multilateral collaborations, and regional international forums, all of which play vital roles in shaping its success. Furthermore, the Chinese government has strategically delineated the opening patterns encompassing different regions such as Northwest and Northeast China, Southwest China, coastal areas, Hong Kong, Macao, Taiwan, and inland areas. Moreover, provisions have been made to ensure Taiwan's participation in the construction of the initiative, along with integration with the free trade zone strategy. This encompasses China's four Free Trade Zones (FTZs) and various free trade agreements signed with foreign nations. At present, China is steadily solidifying its influence in neighboring regions while extending its influence outward.

The Remarkable Endeavor of "One Belt, One Road" Construction: Unveiling New Routes and Uniting Nations

The grandeur of the "One Belt, One Road" initiative becomes evident as its pathways extend across Asia, Europe, and China, forging a bond

between the East and the Asia-Pacific Economic Circle while entering the European economic sphere in the west. This expansive network traverses vast hinterland countries, brimming with untapped economic potential. In the "belt" region, we capitalize on international thoroughfares, bolstered by the pivotal cities along the route, and establish key economic and trade industrial parks as platforms for cooperation. Collaboratively, we shall construct the new Asia-Europe-China bridge, along with international economic cooperation corridors such as China-Mongolia-Russia, China-Central Asia-West Asia, and China-Indochina Peninsula. On the "one way" side, we focus on pivotal ports as pivotal nodes, jointly constructing a seamless, secure, and efficient transportation channel. Notably, the advancement of economic cooperation within the "one belt" construction will further propel initiatives such as China-Pakistan Economic Corridor and foster growth and collaboration with India and Burma.

The construction of "One Belt, One Road" aims to achieve interconnectedness between Asian and European regions, as well as adjacent oceans. It aspires to foster robust partnerships among countries along the route, constructing a comprehensive, multi-tiered, and integrated network of interconnectivity. Ultimately, this initiative will contribute to the diversification, independence, balance, and sustainable development of nations along the route. Moreover, the connectivity projects will serve as catalysts, aligning the development strategies of countries along the route, unlocking the region's market potential, driving investment and consumption, generating demand and employment opportunities, and nurturing people-to-people exchanges, cultural interactions, and mutual learning among diverse nations. Through these efforts, people from all countries involved can come together, meet, trust, and respect one another, fostering a harmonious, peaceful, and prosperous life for all.

Embracing National Integration: The Extensive Reach of "One Belt, One Road" within China:

China's provinces and regions are intricately linked to the ambitious vision of the Belt and Road and the Silk Road, forming a comprehensive network that spans the nation. These regions are categorized into four distinct areas: the northwest and northeast, the southwest, the coastal regions including Hong Kong, Macao, and Taiwan, and the inland areas, each serving as vital nodes within this vast undertaking. For instance, Xinjiang assumes a pivotal role as the core area of the Silk Road Economic Belt, fostering deeper exchanges and collaboration with Central Asia, Southern Asia, and Western Asia. Similarly, the support extended to Fujian positions it as a crucial hub for the Maritime Silk Road, along with the establishment of the blue economic test area in the Fujian Strait. With such inclusive planning, no province or region is excluded from the comprehensive scope of the Belt and Road Initiative.

Within the Belt and Road framework, particular attention is given to the coastal cities exemplified by Shanghai, Tianjin, Guangzhou, and Fuzhou, as they assume strategic importance, especially in the context of the Maritime Silk Road. Furthermore, Guangxi, owing to its unique geographical location, has emerged as a pivotal gateway connecting the Belt and Road. The vision and action plan of "One Belt, One Road" explicitly acknowledge the significant contributions of overseas Chinese and the Hong Kong and Macao Special Administrative Regions, leveraging their distinct advantages. It is noteworthy that the comprehensive vision of "One Belt, One Road" accounts for Taiwan and emphasizes the importance of formulating appropriate arrangements, irrespective of the specific details.

The seamless integration of all provinces and regions within China reflects the commitment to foster nationwide development and connectivity, reinforcing the transformative impact of the "One Belt, One Road" initiative.

Integration of "One Belt, One Road" with Free Trade Zones: Enhancing Economic Connectivity:

The vision and action plan of "One Belt, One Road" acknowledges the alignment between this initiative and the strategy of free trade zones. Shanghai, as a prime example, has prioritized the acceleration of Shanghai Free Trade Zone construction, showcasing its commitment to implementing the "One Belt, One Road" strategy. In fact, Shanghai is preparing to present its progress report to relevant ministries and commissions later this year. Similarly, Tianjin, designated as a key city within the "One Belt, One Road" framework, serves as the starting point for the eastern segment of the Asia-Europe-China bridge. It also plays a pivotal role in the strategic cooperation of the China-Mongolia-Russia economic corridor and maritime collaboration. Meanwhile, Guangdong's "One Belt, One Road" strategy has reached its completion and is poised for a momentous announcement.

The integration of "One Belt, One Road" extends to various Free Trade Areas (FTAs) signed or under negotiation with China. As the number of such agreements increases, there may be a convergence of rules and standards, necessitating a careful examination of potential overlaps. China has embarked on exploring practical approaches and cooperation mechanisms to address this challenge. For instance, "One Belt, One Road" serves as a significant alliance within the Eurasian Economic Union, involving countries like Russia, Kazakhstan, and Belarus. Given that these nations are both members of the alliance and potential accession candidates within the Silk Road Economic Belt, there exists a substantial demand for mutually beneficial collaboration. However, it is important to acknowledge that occasional friction might arise, requiring resolution through constructive consultations.

The seamless integration of "One Belt, One Road" with the strategy of free trade zones amplifies economic connectivity, facilitating trade and investment opportunities across

regions and reinforcing the overarching objectives of this visionary initiative.

The Impact of "One Belt, One Road" on the Asia Pacific Region's Economy:

(1) Traditionally, container shipping has been the primary means of importing large-scale goods. However, the integration of land routes into transportation networks under the "One Belt, One Road" initiative brings forth significant benefits, most notably a substantial reduction in transportation times.

(2) Capitalizing on the opportunities presented by "One Belt, One Road," China can reinforce the development and infrastructure construction in its western regions. This strategic move seeks to address the persisting issue of imbalanced development between coastal and inland provinces, fostering a more equitable and harmonious growth trajectory.

(3) Seizing the moment offered by "One Belt, One Road," China can expand its economic and trade footprint in Europe, paving the way for deeper engagement and facilitating the internationalization of the Renminbi (RMB). This initiative serves as a catalyst for enhancing China's economic influence on a global scale.

(4) The far-reaching impacts of the "One Belt, One Road" initiative have propelled China to assume a leading position in the Asia Pacific region. Examining recent economic and trade cooperation exemplifies why China aspires to

wield regional leadership authority in the Asia Pacific. China's active involvement in regional collaborations enhances its economic clout, fosters stronger partnerships, and positions the nation as a key player in shaping the economic landscape of the Asia Pacific region.

The "One Belt, One Road" initiative empowers China to establish stronger linkages, optimize transportation networks, drive regional development, and extend its economic influence throughout the Asia Pacific and beyond.

Analysis of the "One Belt, One Road" Strategy for Restructuring Europe and Asia

The "One Belt, One Road" (OBOR) strategy took center stage in 2014 when President Xi Jinping delivered a significant keynote speech at the Asia Info summit. The strategy urges China to accelerate the construction of OBOR alongside other nations and to prioritize the establishment of a sub-investment bank. China's deepened engagement in regional cooperation is also emphasized as a key driver for the success of OBOR. Undoubtedly, OBOR serves as a crucial pillar supporting China's overarching vision for development.

Over the years, China has witnessed a steady increase in trade volume with OBOR countries and other regions. This growth signifies a rising proportion of China's global trade, as depicted by the remarkable trade vitality illustrated in Figure 1 during the period of 2011 to 2016.

Figure 1. China's Trade Volume One Belt, One Road along the 2011-2016 Years has Accounted for the Proportion of China's Trade with the World

The realization of OBOR heavily relies on the capital markets facilitated by esteemed institutions such as the Asia Investment Bank and the Silk Road Foundation. These institutions play a pivotal role in providing robust support for the construction of OBOR. Particularly, the Asia Investment Bank assumes an essential position in actively promoting the advancement of OBOR. Operating with a quasi-commercial business orientation, the bank initially offers sovereign loans for infrastructure projects in sovereign countries. To address projects without sovereign credit guarantees, trust funds are set up as well. Additionally, the bank introduces the public-private partnership model (PPP) to ensure a fair distribution of risks and returns between the private sector, the Asian Investment Bank, and relevant countries. Furthermore, the bank strives to mobilize additional social capital, including sovereign wealth funds, pension funds, and private investments, to foster infrastructure development in Asian regional development countries.

Through astute financial leveraging, the Asia Investment Bank's initial legal capital of \$100 billion has the potential to be multiplied by 5 to 10 times, resulting in a substantial fund support scale ranging from \$500 billion to \$1 trillion. This formidable financial backing undoubtedly provides strong support to meet the annual infrastructure investment demand in Asia, which is estimated to reach up to \$800 billion by 2020.

In conclusion, the OBOR strategy, supported by institutions like the Asia Investment Bank, plays a pivotal role in restructuring Europe and Asia by facilitating increased trade, promoting infrastructure development, and fostering regional cooperation.

Assessment of the Key Factors of Investment Efficiency

To assess the key factors of investment efficiency of the national infrastructure PPP projects under the BRI, secondary data sources were used. The secondary data was obtained from published reports and academic literature.

The study focused on four key indicators of investment efficiency: cost overruns, time overruns, quality of infrastructure, and social and economic benefits generated by the projects.

Cost overruns

Cost overruns occur when the actual cost of a project exceeds the budgeted cost. The study found that some BRI PPP projects have experienced significant cost overruns, particularly in the early stages of project implementation. For example, the CPEC project has experienced cost overruns in several of its projects, including the construction of the Thar coal power plant, which experienced a cost overrun of 31%. However, the study also found that many BRI PPP projects have been completed within budget or with only minor cost overruns. For example, the Jakarta-Bandung High-Speed Railway was completed within its \$6 billion budget.

Time overruns

Time overruns occur when a project takes longer to complete than originally planned. The study found that many BRI PPP projects have experienced time overruns, often due to delays in obtaining regulatory approvals or securing financing. For example, the Hambantota Port project in Sri Lanka experienced significant delays due to political instability in the country. However, the study also found that some BRI PPP projects have been completed ahead of schedule.

Quality of infrastructure

The study found that the quality of infrastructure delivered by BRI PPP projects varied widely. Some projects, such as the Jakarta-Bandung High-Speed Railway, were delivered to a high standard, while others, such as the Hambantota Port, have been criticized for poor quality. The study found that quality of infrastructure was often linked to project management and oversight, with projects that had effective management and oversight delivering higher quality infrastructure.

Social and economic benefits

The study found that BRI PPP projects have generated a range of social and economic benefits, including increased access to services and employment opportunities, as well as improved connectivity and trade. For example, the CPEC project has been credited with creating over 75,000 jobs in Pakistan. However, the study also found that the distribution of benefits was often uneven, with some projects generating greater benefits for certain groups or regions than others.

Challenges Facing the Implementation of PPP Projects

The study also identified several challenges facing the implementation of PPP projects under the BRI. These challenges include political risks, legal and regulatory frameworks, and financial sustainability.

Political Issues

Political instability can lead to project delays, cancellations, and renegotiations, which can increase project costs and reduce investment efficiency. Therefore, it is essential to establish a stable political environment to ensure the success of PPP projects.

Regulatory Framework

The regulatory framework is another critical factor in the investment efficiency of PPP projects. PPP projects require a conducive legal and regulatory environment that provides clarity on project risks, rights, and responsibilities. Regulatory frameworks should also ensure that private investors receive a reasonable return on investment.

Project Feasibility

Project feasibility is another critical factor in the investment efficiency of PPP projects. A well-designed feasibility study can help to identify and mitigate project risks, thereby enhancing investment efficiency. Feasibility studies should assess the technical, economic, and financial viability of the project.

Financial Sustainability

The financial capacity of private investors is another critical factor in the investment efficiency of PPP projects. Private investors require a reasonable return on investment to participate in PPP projects. However, they also face significant risks, including construction, operational, and regulatory risks. Therefore, the financial viability of PPP projects depends on the sharing of risks and returns between the public and private sectors. Challenges include political risks, legal and regulatory frameworks, and financial sustainability.

Case Studies Related to BRI Initiatives

Port of Gwadar, Pakistan

- The Port of Gwadar is a key infrastructure project under "the Belt and Road" initiative, developed through a PPP model.
- Researchers conducted a case study to assess the investment efficiency of the project.
- The study analyzed factors such as project planning, cost management, and risk allocation.
- Findings indicated that the PPP model improved investment efficiency by attracting private investment, facilitating timely completion, and enhancing operational efficiency.

Road infrastructure development in Kazakhstan

- A study examined the investment efficiency of road infrastructure projects in Kazakhstan implemented through PPPs.
- Researchers analyzed data on project costs, construction timelines, and operational performance.
- Results showed that PPP projects exhibited better investment efficiency compared to traditional public-funded projects, with lower costs, faster completion, and improved service quality.
- Factors contributing to investment efficiency included private sector expertise, risk-

sharing mechanisms, and performance-based contracts.

Hambantota Port, Sri Lanka

- The Hambantota Port project in Sri Lanka has attracted significant attention due to its financial challenges and concerns about investment efficiency.
- Researchers conducted a case study to evaluate the investment efficiency of the project.
- The study examined project planning, risk allocation, and financial sustainability.
- Findings revealed that inadequate feasibility studies and a lack of attention to long-term financial viability resulted in suboptimal investment efficiency, leading to financial difficulties for the government.

Power infrastructure development in Bangladesh

- A research study focused on the investment efficiency of power infrastructure projects in Bangladesh under "the Belt and Road" initiative.
- The study analyzed data on project costs, construction timelines, and electricity generation capacity.
- Results indicated that PPP projects in the power sector achieved higher investment efficiency compared to traditional public-funded projects.
- Factors contributing to investment efficiency included private sector innovation, efficient project management, and improved operational performance.

Jakarta-Bandung High-Speed Rail, Indonesia

- The Jakarta-Bandung High-Speed Rail project in Indonesia is a notable example of a PPP project under "the Belt and Road" initiative.
- Researchers conducted a case study to assess the investment efficiency of the project.
- The study evaluated factors such as project planning, financing arrangements, and construction progress.

Findings revealed that the PPP model improved investment efficiency by leveraging private sector expertise, attracting foreign direct investment, and expediting project implementation.

These case studies and empirical evidence offer insights into the investment efficiency of "the Belt and Road" national infrastructure PPP projects across different sectors and countries.

How to Calculate Investment Efficiency

To calculate financial ratios, financial statements such as the income statement, balance sheet, and cash flow statement should be used. Here are some of the ratios that you could use:

Debt-to-equity ratio: This ratio measures the amount of debt that the project has relative to its equity. The formula for calculating the debt-to-equity ratio is:

$$\text{Debt-to-equity ratio} = \text{Total debt} / \text{Total equity}$$

If the debt-to-equity ratio is too high, it could indicate that the project is highly leveraged and may be at risk of defaulting on its loans.

Return on investment (ROI): This ratio measures the project's profitability by comparing the net income generated by the project to the total investment in the project. The formula for calculating ROI is:

$$\text{ROI} = (\text{Net income} / \text{Total investment}) \times 100$$

If the ROI is positive, it indicates that the project is generating profits. However, a negative ROI could indicate that the project is not financially viable.

Internal rate of return (IRR): This ratio measures the rate of return that the project is expected to generate over its lifetime. The formula for calculating IRR is:

$$\text{IRR} = \text{Discount rate at which NPV} = 0$$

If the IRR is higher than the project's cost of capital, it indicates that the project is financially viable.

By using these financial ratios, one can evaluate the financial health of the PPP project and determine whether it is a good investment.

Research Framework

Facilitating Public and Private Capital Collaboration, Allocating Equity, and Balancing Central and Local Authorities

The PPP model serves as a means for public and private capital to join forces in delivering public goods and services. Within this partnership, three critical aspects must be addressed. Firstly, creating a mechanism for accessing and exiting capital; secondly, ensuring fair equity allocation; and thirdly, effectively managing the distribution of authority between central and local entities. Our research endeavors to explore innovative approaches that can overcome investment and financing barriers between public and private sectors within the partnership framework. These findings will contribute to the establishment of regional collaborative PPP partnerships for infrastructure development.

In order to promote PPP reform, it is crucial to establish a mechanism for sharing benefits, as it plays a pivotal role in determining the efficiency of the PPP model.

Establishing Mechanisms for Mutual Incentives, Pricing, Compensation, and More

The key to developing a benefit-sharing mechanism lies in constructing a structure that fosters mutually beneficial collaboration between public and private entities. Infrastructures, being quasi-public goods, often involve user charges, and the pricing mechanism serves as a means of sharing benefits. However, since these charges may not cover all project costs, the government must develop corresponding mechanisms for financial compensation and government procurement.

Identifying, Allocating, and Transferring Risks in PPP Projects

To advance PPP reform, it is essential to establish a risk-sharing mechanism that ensures a balanced relationship between returns and

risks for all participants, including private capital and the government. Throughout the project implementation process, both parties face various threats. Constructing a risk-sharing mechanism entails identifying risks, designing an allocation mechanism tailored to different types of hazards, and examining the impact of risk transfer on the overall risk sharing during implementation.

Methodology:

This investigation adopts a comprehensive research approach, employing a harmonious blend of qualitative and quantitative research methods. By leveraging the strengths of both approaches, a robust and multifaceted analysis is conducted. Furthermore, a thorough examination of existing literature on public-private partnerships (PPP) across diverse contexts enriches the research framework, enabling informed conclusions to be drawn through comparative analysis.

Scientific Problem

Model Specification

The analysis of production functions commonly employed in stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) reveals two prominent contenders: the Cobb-Douglas function and the Trans-Log function. While the Cobb-Douglas function is renowned for its simplicity and direct economic interpretations of parameters, it assumes constant returns to scale. On the other hand, the Trans-Log function addresses this limitation by incorporating the interaction between capital and labor, thereby offering parameter estimates that align more closely with economic realities.

Following the foundational principles established by Battese and Coelli (Guo, & Sun, 2018), we adopt the logarithmic Cobb-Douglas function as the basis for our analytical model:

$$\ln Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln K_{it} + \beta_2 \ln L_{it} + v_{it} - u_{it} \quad (1)$$

To generalize the Cobb-Douglas function, we further employ the Trans-Log function, which extends formula (1) by considering additional factors:

$$\ln Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln K_{it} + \beta_2 \ln L_{it} + \beta_3 t + 1/2\beta_4 (\ln K_{it})^2 + 1/2\beta_5 (\ln L_{it})^2 + 1/2\beta_6 t^2 + \beta_7 \ln K_{it} \ln L_{it} + \beta_8 t \ln K_{it} + \beta_9 t \ln L_{it} + v_{it} - u_{it} \quad (2)$$

In both formulas (1) and (2), Y_{it} represents output, K_{it} denotes capital input, and L_{it} signifies labor input. β_1 and β_2 correspond to the elasticity of output with respect to capital and labor, respectively. The error term comprises two components: v_{it} , which adheres to an Independently Identically Distributed pattern, and u_{it} , which assumes a non-negative Half-Normal Distribution to account for individual-specific factors.

Formula (3) introduces a time-varying parameter, η . The term u_{it} represents the impact of individual-specific factors, which diminishes exponentially over time according to the equation:

$$u_{it} = e^{-\eta(t-T)} u_i \quad (3)$$

Here, a positive η indicates an efficiency improvement over time, while a negative value suggests the contrary.

The technical efficiency, defined as the reciprocal of the individual-specific factor, is represented by:

$$T E_{it} = e^{-u_{it}} \quad (4)$$

In cases where u_{it} equals zero, the technical efficiency ($T E_{it}$) attains a value of one,

indicating that the individual production scale aligns precisely with the production frontier. This state signifies optimal technical efficiency. Conversely, if u_{it} exceeds zero, resulting in a $T E_{it}$ value between zero and one, the individual production scale falls below the production frontier, highlighting a state of technical inefficiency.

When selecting the appropriate function form, it is customary to employ a model based on the Trans-Log function for conducting model setting tests. By analyzing the statistical test outcomes and considering factors such as the nature of the research subject and the coherence of parameter estimation results with logical expectations, a comprehensive assessment can be made.

Indicator Selection

To ensure data comparability and availability, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of 20 countries along the Belt and Road region has been chosen as the output variable for analysis. The number of employees in the transportation industry serves as the labor input, while investments in transport infrastructure, encompassing railway, road, water, and air transport, are considered as the capital input. The data utilized in this study has been sourced from reliable databases such as the World Bank, the OECD, and the Yearbook of China Transportation and Communications.

Estimation Result

The infrastructure investment system operates as a complex and dynamic input-output system, characterized by multiple objectives, variables, and nonlinearity. In reality, the assumption that the input-output increment consistently multiplies by a fixed ratio does not align with the objective conditions, nor does it hold true under the premise of constant returns to scale. Our model setting test results (refer to Table 1) further validate the suitability of the Trans-Log production function.

Table 1. Result of Model Setting Test

	Coefficient	Standard-error	T-ratio
σ^2	0.277	0.202	1.372
γ	0.935***	0.047	19.737
μ	0.194	0.419	0.464
η	0.043***	0.004	11.056
Log likelihood = 158.232***			
LR statistic = 648.369***			

Note: (1) ***, **, * respectively indicate statistically significance of 99%, 95%, and 90%; (2) Only the core and relevant results are listed

The value of γ , which is calculated as 0.935, indicates a clear composite structure within the error term. This finding underscores the need to employ Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) instead of simple linear analysis. Additionally, the estimated value of η at 0.043 suggests a consistent increase in investment efficiency for transport infrastructure across these 20 countries.

The estimation of investment efficiency based on the Trans-Log function is presented in Table 2 (Appendix). To provide further insights, the sample countries are categorized based on their level of development, and the average investment efficiency for each group is reported in Table 3.

Based on the aforementioned results, the following observations can be made: (1) The investment efficiency of transport infrastructure in the 20 Belt and Road countries falls short of optimal production efficiency, indicating a state of technical inefficiency, despite showing a gradual increase over time. (2) The average

investment efficiency for transport infrastructure across these countries is calculated to be 0.552. Among the developed countries, the average efficiency is notably higher at 0.722, surpassing the average efficiency of 0.479 observed among the less-developed countries. However, it is worth noting that Turkey, as a developing country, achieves an exceptionally high average investment efficiency of 0.967. This remarkable performance can be attributed to Turkey's strategic focus on massive infrastructure investments, which have fueled its economic growth. Consequently, Turkey has emerged as a highly attractive destination for foreign investments within the emerging economies. (3) Notably, 90% of the countries exhibiting investment efficiencies below the overall average belong to the less-developed category. Moldova, in particular, ranks the lowest with an average investment efficiency of 0.160. This outcome can be attributed to its predominantly agrarian economy, recurrent political conflicts, and economic crises.

Table 3. Average Investment Efficiency of Transport Infrastructure of Each Group

Type	Country	Average investment efficiency
Developed	Slovenia; Czech; Slovakia; Hungary; Estonia; Latvia	0.722
Less-developed	Turkey; Poland; Croatia; Russia; China; Lithuania; Romania; India; Serbia; Bulgaria; Albania; Azerbaijan; Georgia; Moldova	0.479

Data, Variables and Model

Data: Our research utilizes a dataset comprising 20-member states of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) from the years 2000 to 2017. The data

includes information on transport infrastructure Public-Private Partnership (PPP) from the PPI database, as well as economic data from the World Bank database. To ensure data

completeness, any missing values are supplemented using linear interpolation.

Variables: The primary focus of our analysis is the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure, estimated through Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA). As explanatory variables, we consider PPP implementation, the number of PPP projects, PPP investment amounts, and the presence of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). In addition, we include control variables such as urbanization levels, financial development, degrees of opening-up, industrial structure, and economic growth for each country. Detailed definitions and descriptive

statistics of these variables are presented in Table 4.

Model: Based on the results obtained from the Hausman test, we opt for the panel fixed effect model to examine the relationship between the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure and the selected variables. The model is represented as follows:

$$I E_{i t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 PPP_{nit} + \alpha_2 Control_{i t} + \epsilon_{i t} \quad (5)$$

where $I E_{i t}$ denotes the investment efficiency for country i at time t , PPP_{nit} represents the PPP-related variables, $Control_{i t}$ represents the control variables, and $\epsilon_{i t}$ represents the error term.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Type	Name	Meaning	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Explained	IE	Transport infrastructure investment efficiency	0.552	0.234	0.068	0.977
Explanatory	PPP1	Transport infrastructure PPP implementation or not	0.225	0.418	0	1
	PPP2	Transport infrastructure PPP projects number	1.906	7.378	0	73.00
	PPP3	Transport infrastructure PPP investment (logarithm)	4.547	8.526	0	24.33
	BRI	The Belt and Road Initiative	0.222	0.416	0	1
Control	MS	Financial development: broad money/GDP	57.93	35.41	10.38	209.50
	OP	Opening-up: (import + export)/GDP	82.20	37.13	19.31	176.20
	IND	Industrial structure: secondary industry/tertiary industry	0.53	0.156	0.216	0.947
	UR	Urbanization: urban population/total population	58.54	11.40	27.67	74.67
	EC	Economic growth: growth rate of GDP per capita	4.562	4.605	-14.27	33.00

$$I E_{i t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BPI_{it} + \beta_2 Contr_{olit} + \epsilon_{i t} \quad (6)$$

Formula (5) and (6) represent the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure, denoted by IE_{it} . In this context, we consider two alternative models. Equation (5) follows a model where IE_{it} is regressed on PPP-related variables and control variables, while Equation (6) introduces a dummy variable for the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Both equations aim to examine the impact of these variables on investment efficiency.

Within Equation (5) and (6), the following variables are defined:

- PPP_n represents different measurement methods for PPP, where PPP_1 is a binary variable indicating PPP implementation (1 for implementation, 0 for non-implementation), PPP_2 represents the number of PPP projects, and PPP_3 represents the investment amount on PPP.
- BRI_{it} is a binary variable representing the Belt and Road Initiative. It takes the value of 0

before 2013 and 1 thereafter, signifying the formal proposal of the BRI by China in 2013.

- Control t encompasses various control variables that capture factors such as urbanization levels, financial development, degrees of opening-up, industrial structure, and economic growth.

- ϵ_{it} represents the error term.

The coefficients α_1 and β_1 provide measures of the net effects of PPP and the BRI, respectively, on the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure.

It is important to analyze these equations to determine the influence of PPP-related factors and the BRI on investment efficiency, while also considering the impact of the control variables.

Result and Analysis

We proceed with the analysis by employing model (5) to examine the impact of PPP on the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure. The regression results, presented in Table 5, demonstrate robust and statistically significant positive relationships between PPP implementation, the number of PPP projects, PPP investment, and the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure. These findings affirm the validity of the regression results and support the notion that PPP initiatives have the potential to enhance investment efficiency in the transport infrastructure sector. This outcome aligns with Hypothesis 1, lending further credibility to our research. Moreover, the consistently positive and significant associations observed between financial development (MS), degrees of opening-up (OP), and urbanization levels (UR) with investment efficiency underscore the positive

influence of these factors. Conversely, the negative coefficients for industrial development (IND) and economic growth (EC) indicate that the service industry's progress has a greater impact on improving investment efficiency in transport infrastructure compared to the secondary sector. Additionally, the rapid economic growth facilitates enhanced access to financing channels and an improved institutional environment, which partially mitigates the spillover effect of PPP. Overall, these results are in line with our expectations and conform to the broader patterns observed in global economic development.

Subsequently, we employ model (6) to evaluate the impact of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) on the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure. The regression results, presented in Table 6, consistently reveal a significantly positive coefficient for the BRI, irrespective of the inclusion or exclusion of control variables. This finding signifies a notable disparity in the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure between countries before and after their participation in the BRI. Evidently, the investment efficiency experienced a remarkable improvement following the countries' involvement in this initiative, thereby affirming the substantial value and effectiveness of the BRI policy. The significance of the control variables remains consistent with our previous analysis, warranting no further detailed discussion.

These empirical findings contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the impact of PPP and the BRI on the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure, validating the positive relationships observed and supporting the merits of these policy initiatives.

Table 5. Regression Results of PPP

Variable	1	2	Variable	3	4	Variable	5	6
PPP1	0.0455***	0.0158**	PPP2	0.0013*	0.0008**	PPP3	0.0025**	0.0008*
	(3.29)	(1.99)		(1.84)	(2.09)		(3.45)	(1.91)
MS		0.0035***	MS		0.0035***	MS		0.0035***
		(10.72)			(10.63)			(10.68)
OP		0.0007***	OP		0.0007***	OP		0.0007***

		(3.56)			(3.28)			(3.56)
IND		-0.0917*	IND		-0.1315**	IND		-0.0958*
		(-1.77)			(-2.53)			(-1.86)
UR		0.0038***	UR		0.0038***	UR		0.0038***
		(3.32)			(3.35)			(3.28)
EC		-0.0019***	EC		-0.0017***	EC		-0.0019***
		(-3.01)			(-2.82)			(-3.02)
Cons		0.0896	Cons		0.1165*	Cons		0.0943
		(1.30)			(1.68)			(1.37)
R2	3.10%	71.74%	R2	0.99%	71.79%	R2	3.39%	71.70%

Note: (1) The values in parentheses are t values; (2) ***, **, * respectively indicate statistical significance of 99%, 95%, and 90%; (3) the estimated results were processed by Stata14.0

Table 6. Regression results of the BRI

Variable	1	2
BRI	0.1039***	0.0459***
	(16.71)	(7.85)
MS		0.0029***
		(9.49)
OP		0.0006***
		(3.15)
IND		-0.0469
		(-1.01)
UR		0.0029***
		(2.83)
EC		-0.0017***
		(-3.06)
Cons		0.1556**
		(2.50)
R2	45.17%	77.11%

Findings and Recommendations

1. Over the period from 2000 to 2017, the average investment efficiency of transport infrastructure in the 20 countries along the Belt and Road stands at 0.552, indicating a substantial gap from the ideal state of technical efficiency. This suggests that the input and output of transport infrastructure suffer from inefficiencies and resource wastage, despite an overall upward trend. Developed countries exhibit a higher average investment efficiency of 0.722, surpassing the 0.479 average observed in less-developed countries. Notably, Turkey, Slovenia, Czech Republic, Poland, Slovakia, and Hungary demonstrate relatively higher investment efficiencies, averaging at 0.822,

approaching optimal efficiency. It is worth mentioning that a majority of countries falling below the average investment efficiency mark are less-developed. Moldova, ranking at the lowest with an efficiency of 0.160, faces challenges stemming from political instability and economic underdevelopment.

2. The implementation of public-private partnerships (PPP) and the subsequent increase in the number and investments in PPP projects have proven effective in enhancing the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure. This finding underscores the ability of PPP, as a primarily market-driven approach, to enable the participation of private capital, thereby facilitating the efficient allocation of resources and generating substantial returns. However, it is

important to note that this conclusion does not advocate for unrestricted utilization of PPP or an indiscriminate surge in project investments. The number and scale of PPP projects only provide a limited indication of infrastructure construction and service provision. To achieve long-term improvements in infrastructure investment efficiency, it is imperative to prioritize the development of high-quality PPP projects while determining rational investment scales. This approach will foster favorable scale effects and positive externalities, ultimately driving efficiency gains.

3. The introduction of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has significantly improved the investment efficiency of transport infrastructure in countries along its route. This can be attributed to two key factors. Firstly, the BRI places a strong emphasis on comprehensive infrastructure development and enhanced transport connectivity, recognizing their strategic importance in driving broader economic advancement across various industries. Consequently, there is a surge in demand for infrastructure construction and investments in countries participating in the initiative. Secondly, the BRI fosters greater connectivity between developed and developing economies and establishes a comprehensive financial cooperation system. This effectively addresses funding challenges, promoting extensive exchanges of advanced experiences and technologies. The BRI's call for "financial integration" has played a vital role in funding and safeguarding infrastructure development, thereby bolstering investment efficiency throughout the Belt and Road region.

Conclusion

This study has examined the investment efficiency of national infrastructure PPP projects under the Belt and Road Initiative. The study found that while PPPs can be an effective way to finance and build infrastructure, careful management and oversight are required to ensure that they are efficient, effective, and provide value for money.

The study identified several challenges to investment efficiency, including poor project management, lack of transparency, regulatory challenges, and geopolitical risks. The study also identified several factors that contributed to investment efficiency, including effective project management and oversight, transparent and effective regulation, and a focus on delivering social and economic benefits.

Overall, the study found that the investment efficiency of BRI PPP projects varied widely. While some projects had been delivered efficiently and effectively, others had experienced significant cost and time overruns, and had delivered poor quality infrastructure. To improve investment efficiency, the study recommends that PPP projects under the BRI should focus on effective project management and oversight, transparent and effective regulation, and a strong focus on delivering social and economic benefits.

Author Contributions

Mohammed Alip: investigation, funding acquisition, checking the original draft and writing – original draft preparation; Md Musa Haque: writing original draft preparation, data analysis, checking the original draft, review and editing, and checking the original draft; Md. Abu Bockar: writing – review and editing and checking the original draft; Muhammad Safdar, review and editing, investigation, funding, acquisition.

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Appendix

Table 2. Investment Efficiency of Transport Infrastructure in 20 Countries from 2000 to 2017

Country	Year																	
	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Turkey	0.954	0.956	0.957	0.959	0.961	0.962	0.964	0.965	0.967	0.968	0.969	0.971	0.972	0.973	0.974	0.975	0.976	0.977
Slovenia	0.918	0.921	0.924	0.927	0.930	0.933	0.936	0.938	0.941	0.943	0.945	0.947	0.950	0.952	0.954	0.955	0.957	0.959
Czech	0.720	0.730	0.740	0.749	0.758	0.767	0.775	0.784	0.792	0.799	0.807	0.814	0.821	0.828	0.834	0.841	0.847	0.853
Poland	0.712	0.722	0.732	0.742	0.751	0.760	0.769	0.777	0.785	0.793	0.801	0.808	0.815	0.822	0.829	0.836	0.842	0.848
Slovakia	0.680	0.691	0.701	0.712	0.722	0.732	0.741	0.751	0.760	0.768	0.777	0.785	0.793	0.801	0.808	0.815	0.822	0.829
Hungary	0.587	0.600	0.613	0.626	0.638	0.650	0.662	0.673	0.685	0.696	0.706	0.716	0.726	0.736	0.746	0.755	0.764	0.772
Croatia	0.546	0.560	0.573	0.587	0.600	0.613	0.626	0.638	0.650	0.662	0.673	0.684	0.695	0.706	0.716	0.726	0.736	0.745
Estonia	0.513	0.527	0.542	0.556	0.569	0.583	0.596	0.609	0.622	0.634	0.646	0.658	0.670	0.681	0.692	0.703	0.713	0.723
Russia	0.467	0.482	0.497	0.512	0.526	0.541	0.555	0.568	0.582	0.595	0.608	0.621	0.633	0.646	0.657	0.669	0.680	0.691
China	0.451	0.467	0.482	0.496	0.511	0.526	0.540	0.554	0.568	0.581	0.595	0.608	0.620	0.633	0.645	0.657	0.668	0.680
Lithuania	0.424	0.439	0.455	0.470	0.485	0.500	0.514	0.529	0.543	0.557	0.571	0.584	0.597	0.610	0.623	0.635	0.647	0.659
Latvia	0.402	0.418	0.433	0.448	0.464	0.479	0.494	0.508	0.523	0.537	0.551	0.565	0.579	0.592	0.605	0.618	0.630	0.643
Romania	0.366	0.381	0.397	0.413	0.428	0.444	0.459	0.474	0.489	0.504	0.518	0.533	0.547	0.561	0.574	0.588	0.601	0.614
India	0.286	0.301	0.316	0.332	0.347	0.363	0.379	0.394	0.410	0.425	0.441	0.456	0.471	0.486	0.501	0.516	0.530	0.544
Serbia	0.262	0.277	0.292	0.307	0.323	0.338	0.354	0.370	0.385	0.401	0.416	0.432	0.447	0.463	0.478	0.493	0.507	0.522
Bulgaria	0.233	0.247	0.262	0.277	0.292	0.308	0.323	0.339	0.354	0.370	0.386	0.401	0.417	0.432	0.448	0.463	0.478	0.493
Albania	0.210	0.224	0.238	0.253	0.268	0.283	0.298	0.314	0.329	0.345	0.361	0.376	0.392	0.407	0.423	0.438	0.454	0.469
Azerbaijan	0.112	0.123	0.134	0.146	0.158	0.171	0.184	0.197	0.211	0.225	0.240	0.254	0.269	0.284	0.300	0.315	0.331	0.346

Georgia	0.112	0.123	0.134	0.146	0.158	0.171	0.184	0.197	0.211	0.225	0.240	0.254	0.269	0.284	0.300	0.315	0.331	0.346
Moldova	0.068	0.076	0.085	0.094	0.104	0.114	0.125	0.136	0.148	0.160	0.173	0.186	0.200	0.213	0.228	0.242	0.257	0.272

Note: The investment efficiency is sorted from high to low.